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Innovation in Education and Transformation of Learning Habits: Uzbekistan Case

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Abstract: Education is one of the most important elements for a society to develop. Because thanks to educated individuals, a certain quality can be achieved in the production process and economic growth can be achieved. Technological advances that are gaining momentum in today's globalizing world also significantly affect the education system. In this process, it is extremely important for educational activities to adapt to changing conditions. In other words, education, which significantly affects the future structure and welfare level of societies, must turn to innovative methods in the global transformation process, adapt to the changes that occur on a global scale, and be prepared for the future periods by meeting the expectations of the society. Therefore, innovation in education is extremely important. In order to realize the necessary change and transformation in education, correct and modern methods should be preferred, the right technologies should be used, new ideas should be kept open, and changes and developments in the education system should be closely followed. In addition, in order for the education process to be more efficient and interesting for students, educational activities should be carried out by effectively using technology and with innovative methods. In summary, it is possible to say that the globalization process significantly affects educational activities. This study will attempt to reveal the effects of innovation, which tends to accelerate due to global developments, on the education system.

Keywords: education, innovation, policy factors, environment factors, resource factors, intervention factors, technological developments.

1. Introduction

Education is an extremely important element in terms of the development of societies in terms of both cultural, social and economic aspects. Thanks to education, it is possible for societies to develop, reach prosperity and become a more cultured society. Therefore, importance should be given to the development of educational activities and the necessary care should be taken in this direction. In order to develop educational activities, developments in the world should be closely followed and these developments should be adapted, and for this purpose, emphasis should be given to innovative applications for the education system. Since the duty of education activities is to sustain the existence of the society by strengthening the cultural ties between individuals living together in the society and to do this on the basis of knowledge, it is of great importance that education activities are open to all innovations of the age. The effective use of developing and changing production techniques by the education system and the development of new education techniques will both positively affect the success of educational activities and contribute to the increase in production volume. Therefore, as in every field, technological innovations should be closely followed in the field of education. Thanks to the developments in the level of education, both the production volume increases and the products become of higher quality. Because thanks to education, the most important part of the production process, the human being, becomes qualified. In other words, education contributes to the qualification of the workforce. In addition, education positively affects technological advances. Therefore, it is possible to say that there is a mutual interaction between education and technological developments. In order for educational activities to be carried out successfully in a country, technological developments must be effectively and successfully incorporated into the education system. Today's educational structure has changed and electronic resources and tools are now given more space in the education process.

2. Innovation in education and the importance of innovation

Innovation in education means making the learning process of students more effective and interesting by using innovative methods and technologies in the education process (Girişimup, 2024). Today, the accelerating technological developments and globalization cause important transformations in terms of society. Educational activities that shape the future of societies are also significantly affected by this transformation and prepare the individuals who make up the society for the future by moving away from traditional education methods and adapting to the changes. In its most general form, it is possible to express innovation in education as the introduction of new ideas that are multidisciplinary and future-oriented, reflecting changes and developments in the education process, instead of traditional methods. This issue includes the use of the right technologies and methods in educational activities, the development of effective processes and the prediction of the future from today (İnoveds, 2024).

According to another definition, innovation means making changes or bringing something to life in a new way. Innovating does not require you to invent something. Innovation in education, on the other hand, is based on implementing innovations in education and approaching problems from different perspectives. Innovation in education includes the creation of an educational environment where students can watch lessons at home and complete homework in class, using more technology in the educational process, and providing both clear and high-quality communication with video tools (Altan, 2023). Innovation in education cannot be considered independent of technology and is expressed as quality. Because education using technology increases quality (Bal İncebacak et al. 2018: 24). Innovation is one of the most important tools used to eliminate inequalities between individuals (Keleşoğlu and Kalaycı, 2017: 73). The effective application of innovation in the education process allows individuals to benefit from education services equally. Therefore, individuals who benefit from this process effectively have the opportunity to develop themselves and in this process, the differences between individuals that make up the society are eliminated. In this respect, innovation is extremely important in terms of enabling the development of a society and eliminating the differences between individuals. Because in this process, all individuals can benefit from education services equally.

The main purposes of innovation in education can be listed as providing higher quality education to individuals who constitute the society, raising individuals who can follow the current events and think in a multi-dimensional way, and making the education process both more effective and goal-oriented. In order to achieve these purposes, it is of great importance that education systems are organized according to contemporary education principles. Because traditional, classical, oppressive and rote-based education systems have begun to give way to free, contemporary and progressive education systems (Taş, 2017: 104). In addition, other purposes of innovation in education are to raise self-confident and aware individuals who can exchange information with each other and to take the current situation in the education system to a further level (Gücüköğlu, 2013). In this respect, it is possible to say that innovation in education is extremely important.

However, the implementation of innovations in the education process is not as easy as it is thought. It is possible to say that there are some factors that affect the implementation of innovations in education. These factors can be listed as; a) Policy Factors b) Environment Factors, c) Resource Factors and d) Intervention Factors. In order for innovations made for education to be successfully implemented, first of all, the root causes of the problems need to be determined correctly. Then, it is also of great importance to conduct sufficient examination and research, to examine alternatives for the solution of the problem and to ensure the support of all stakeholders (Gülşen, 2020:244). At this point, higher education institutions have a great responsibility. Because experts with innovative thinking are trained in universities for the leading fields of informatics and technology, experts are trained with an innovative approach for the innovative economy, and this requires innovation to occur in higher education institutions and for educators in educational institutions to be qualified and innovative (Kazimova and Humbataliyeva, 2019: 348). Uzbekistan is one of the countries that understood the importance of this position early and has made significant investments in this area and continues to do so.

3. Innovation examples in education

Developing various ideas and methods to bring something to life from a different perspective constitutes the basic subject of innovation. Adopting and adopting innovative ideas for education constitutes one of the basic duties of both society and educators. In this context, it is of great importance to prepare teachers for innovative learning methods that are put into practice in order to develop more innovations in education. Innovation should be implemented on a much more widespread scale in the education system in order to make significant progress in the education process. In this context, innovation in education is about implementing a system that helps more students access educational services, facilitating learning, and finally implementing education in a more efficient and quality manner. Innovations in education occur in many different ways in many areas. It is possible to list the examples of innovation in the education process as project-based learning, blended learning, and educational technology. The

most important of these innovation examples is educational technology. Because educational technology generally refers to software, applications, or services used to improve education (Altan, 2023). These applications contribute to the development of education. However, education also has significant effects on technology. Education provides significant contributions to closing the technological gap by providing the necessary manpower for innovation and R&D activities. Developments in the education level of a country contribute to both the development of new technologies and the adaptation and implementation of new technologies developed in other countries. Because it takes time and is costly for employees who cannot reach a certain level of education to adapt to technological developments. Therefore, companies that want to increase their production performance have to prefer an educated workforce (Kılıç and Özbek, 2018: 372). Innovation in education includes many innovative methods and technologies that transform students' learning experiences and prepare them better for the future. Innovative examples such as digital learning platforms, coding and robotics education, personalized learning, project-based learning, flipped classroom, artificial intelligence, gamification, open educational resources and blockchain technology are creating revolutionary changes in education. These innovations allow students to experience a more effective, engaging and productive learning process. Innovation examples in education shape the education systems of the future and contribute to students benefiting from these innovations in the best way possible (Girişimup, 2024). In line with this information, it is possible to say that there is a profitable interaction between education and innovation.

4. Innovation in Uzbekistan education system

Innovative trends in education activities have accelerated recently. In this context, all the possibilities of technology are used while providing education services. Especially online education (distance education with computers) applications are effectively used and computers, smart boards and projection devices are used intensively in the areas where education is provided, education is provided in computer laboratories and thanks to these tools, both education activities are carried out faster and more efficiently and become easier. Because thanks to online education, education can be received without going to any educational environment, that is, without incurring any cost and without any loss of time, and in addition, the education process in educational environments can be both more fun and attractive, and thus students' interest and concentration in the course can increase. This causes the education process to become more efficient. In Uzbekistan, one of the important countries of the global economy, investments aimed at developing the education system have begun to be emphasized in line with the developments in technology. The Uzbekistan government has recently been making important decisions regarding the development of education, and with these decisions, it is aimed for Uzbekistan to become the center of Central Asia in higher education by 2030. In addition, it is stated that the most appropriate way to develop the higher education system is to develop the country, and that universities, research centers within universities, technoparks and innovative technologies in the country can contribute to the development of the education system and thus positively affect the development of industry and the development of the country. In line with this purpose, the Uzbekistan government has started to give more importance to the development of the higher education system in recent years and in this context, it allocates 45% of the total 7.5 billion dollars allocated annually from the state budget to the social sector to education. Thanks to this, the number of higher education institutions has increased to 212 in the country, where there were 77 universities in 2016, with the establishment of 135 universities equipped with new technologies in the last 7 years. Of these 212 universities, 116 are state universities, 66 are private universities, and 30 are international universities established in cooperation with other countries. The capital, Tashkent, which hosts 86 universities, stands out as the city with the most universities in the country. Of the 86 universities in Tashkent, 40 are state universities, and the rest are private universities or international universities established in cooperation with foreign universities (Abdülkerimov, 2023). In line with this information, it is possible to say that there have been significant transformations in the education system of Uzbekistan and that the key to this transformation is technology-intensive innovative trends.

5 Conclusions and Recommendations

Innovation is one of the important concepts of today and in its most general form it means innovation. Education is an extremely important element, first of all, for the development of individuals who make up the society and then for social development accordingly. As in every field, it is extremely important to follow the latest developments in the field of education. In this sense, intensive use of advanced technologies in the education process makes significant contributions to the development of countries. Realizing this reality, Uzbekistan attaches serious importance to innovation in education and focuses on investments aimed at carrying out educational activities by using new technologies. Within this scope, almost half of the investments in the social field in

Uzbekistan are allocated to educational activities. Thanks to these investments, new technologies have started to be used intensively in all educational institutions, especially universities. In addition, a special importance has been given to higher education, which is seen as the key to the country's development, and in recent years, there has been a very rapid increase in the number of both state and private universities. With this structure, Uzbekistan has made significant progress towards becoming the science center of Central Asia. In addition, in Uzbekistan, developments in the field of education in the world, including technology, are closely followed and these innovations are implemented in the education system in a short time. This facilitates and accelerates the integration of the Uzbek education system into the global education system. In addition, these developments allow individuals in the country to receive better education and contribute to the development of the country's economy. In this context, countries aiming for economic development should give importance to innovation in educational activities and closely follow developments in the world.

References

1. Abdülkerimov, B. (2023). Özbekistan, kalkınmayı yükseköğretim sistemini geliştirerek sağlamayı hedefliyor, <https://www.aa.com.tr/tr/dunya/ozbekistan-kalkinmayi-yuksekogretim-sistemini-gelistirerek-saglamayi-hedefliyor/3059325> (Erişim tarihi: 10.12.2024).
2. Altan, S. (2023). Eğitimde İnovasyon ile Öğrenme Alışkanlıklarını Değiştirmek, Enocta, <https://www.enocta.com/blog/egitimde-inovasyon-ile-ogrenme-aliskanliklarini-degistirmek> (Erişim Tarihi: 08.12.2024).
3. Bal-İncebacak, B., Sarışan-Tungaç, A. ve Yaman, S. (2018). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin gözünden eğitimde yenilik ve inovasyon kavramlarına bir bakış: Metafor analizi. Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi Türk Dünyası Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi Eğitim Dergisi (ESTÜDAM Eğitim Dergisi), 3 (2), 19-29.
4. Girişimup, 2024. Eğitimde İnovasyon örnekleri: Öğrenme Sürecini Dönüştüren Yenilikçi Çözümler, <https://www.girisimup.com/egitimde-inovasyon-orneklere-ogrenme-surecini-donusturen-yenilikci-cozumler/> (Erişim Tarihi: 09.12.2024).
5. Gücükoğlu, B., Ceylan D. Y. ve Dursun, Z., (2013). Etkileşimli Beyaz Tahtalar İçin Arayüz Tasarımı ve İçerik Geliştirme: Millî Eğitim Bakanlığı Coğrafya Dersi Örneği. (Erişim Taihi: 08.12.2024, <http://inet-tr.org.tr/inetconf18/bildiri/81.pdf>
6. Gülşen, C. (2020). Eğitim Yönetiminde Yenilik Uygulamalarının Etkenleri, TURAN-SAM Uluslararası Bilimsel Hakemli Dergisi, 12(48), 244-248.
7. İnoveds, (2024). Eğitimde İnovasyon
8. <https://www.inoveds.com/egitimde-inovasyon-i-11#:~:text=E%C4%9Fitimde%20inovasyon%2C%20geleneksel%20y%C3%B6ntemler%20yerine,e%C4%9Fitim%20s%C3%BCre%C3%A7lerinde%20yer%20almas%C4%B1%20demektir> (Erişim Tarihi: 08.12.2024).
9. Kazimova, E., & Humbataliyeva, S. (2019). Yükseköğretim Kurumlarının Yenilikçi Yönetim Sisteminin Kavramsal Temelleri. Stratejik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi, 3(2), 343-350.
10. Keleşoğlu, S., & Kalaycı, N. (2017). Dördüncü sanayi devriminin eşliğinde yaratıcılık, inovasyon ve eğitim ilişkisi. Yaratıcı Drama Dergisi, 12(1), 69-86.
11. Kılıç, R. & Özbek, R. İ. (2018). Sağlık ve Eğitim Hizmetleri ile Ekonomik Büyüme İlişkisi: OECD Ülkeleri Uygulaması. Ordu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Sosyal Bilimler Araştırmaları Dergisi, 8(2), 369-391.
12. Taş, D. D. S. (2017). İnovasyon, Eğitim ve Küresel İnovasyon Endeksi. Bilge Uluslararası Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi, 1(1), 99-123.